

To Find If There Is Any Relationship Of Craniovertebral Angle With Short Deep Cervical Flexors Strength And Endurance, Suboccipital Muscle Length And Abdominal Endurance - Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Neck pain is common in the general population, with 70% of individuals affected at some time in their lives and 5% to 10% of adults having a disabling neck-pain problem.^[8] Forward head posture is one of the common types of poor head posture seen in patients with neck disorders.^[51] In this study we will find any correlation of craniovertebral angle with different variables.

Objective: Forward head posture is a relatively frequent issue these days. It will develop many linked musculoskeletal diseases. So, purpose of my study is to determine whether the craniovertebral angle is correlated with different variables. By finding that one variable, we can prevent a lot of issues caused by forward head posture.

Materials and Methodology: 30 subjects were randomly selected. Head Posture was calculated using Photography Method. Deep Cervical Strength was measured using CCFT. Suboccipital Length was measured using Inclinometer. Abdominal Endurance was measured using Abdominal Endurance Test.

Results: Data analysis showed that there is no correlation of craniovertebral angle with short deep cervical flexors strength and endurance, suboccipital muscle length and abdominal endurance.

Discussion: Subjects were aware of the fact that they were being evaluated for posture and therefore were able to alter or adjust their posture prior to collection of data. This could result in little variability between relaxed and best posture because students had already altered their normal posture.

Conclusion: The study's findings indicate that there is no discernible relationship between craniovertebral angle and the strength and endurance of the short deep cervical flexors, suboccipital muscle length, or abdominal endurance.

Keywords: Abdominal Endurance, Craniovertebral Angle, Short Deep Cervical Flexors Strength and Endurance, Suboccipital Muscle Length

INTRODUCTION

Seventy percent of people will experience neck pain at some point in their lives; and five to ten percent of adults will have a debilitating neck pain issue.^[8] According to a recent population-based study, roughly one third of young individuals experience stiffness or soreness in their necks once a week.^[19] According to McKenzie and Haughie et al., bad posture causes nonspecific neck discomfort because it puts the neck under unusual physiological demands over an

extended period of time, which weakens the neck muscles.^[4,20] One of the most prevalent forms of bad head posture observed in patients with neck issues is forward head posture.^[51] It was discovered that during a 10-minute computer job, participants with neck symptoms had a higher forward head posture. Similarly, Yip et al. found that compared to people without neck pain, patients with neck discomfort had more forward head postures.^[6] Due to our forward-facing society, the body has had to adjust to a forward head posture as

a result of frequent use of cell phones, computers, TVs, video games, trauma, and even backpacks. Renee Calliet, M.D., states that the load on the spine and its tissue is only 10 pounds if the head weighs 10 pounds and the ear's center is squarely over the shoulder's center. On the other hand, the head's weight will rise by 10 pounds for each inch it moves forward. Forward head posture is associated with a higher incidence of headache, interscapular discomfort, and cervical pain.^[51] One of the most prevalent cervical abnormalities that predisposes people to pathological conditions, including temporomandibular disorders, headaches, neck pain, disorders of the vertebral body, changes in soft tissue length and strength, or even scapula and shoulder dyskinesia, is forward head posture (FHP).^[12,40,41,42,48,50] Untreated FHP may result in persistent or unpleasant disorders such as thoracic outlet syndrome, pinched nerves and blood vessels, muscle and tissue discomfort, fibromyalgia, chronic strains, early degeneration, and arthritis.^[10] Due to these related issues, head posture evaluation has grown in significance in clinical settings while assessing and developing treatment plans for patients with neck discomfort and the other diseases mentioned above.^[20]

According to Panjabi et al., the Osseoligamentous system accounts for 20% to 30% of the cervical spine's mechanical stability, with the neck musculature accounting for 80%. Passive resistance to motion is negligible when the cervical spine is in an upright, neutral position. The longus colli muscle, located anteriorly, and the semispinalis cervicis and cervical multifidus muscles, located posteriorly, comprise the muscular sleeve that supports the cervical segments. Supporting and straightening the cervical lordosis is a fundamental postural function of the longus colli muscle in particular. Furthermore, muscles that attach to the cranium and span the upper cervical motion segments support the craniometrical region. These muscles include the suboccipital extensor, semispinalis, and splenius capitis muscles posteriorly, as well as the longus capitis muscle anteriorly.^[7,30,36,46] Claims that forward head posture may cause physical stimulation and/or the buildup of algic

chemicals that exacerbate pain seem to be the foundation of arguments supporting a connection between forward head posture and neck discomfort. Stretching of the neck's anterior structures, shortening of the posterior muscles, exhaustion and buildup of analgesics in the muscles that counteract the head's propensity to tilt forward, and increases in compressive forces on the cervical apophyseal joints and posterior aspects of the vertebral bodies are all possible mediators of pain.^[43]

Prior research employing the CCFT in individuals with chronic dysfunction and neck discomfort has shown that decreased activation of the DCF muscles is linked to greater activation of the superficial flexor muscles.¹ According to anecdotal evidence, neck pain causes the cervical flexor muscles to malfunction. Additionally, it has been shown that patients with neck discomfort have weaker cervical flexor muscles when using basic clinical mechanical tests.^[12,26,39] The equilibrium between the deep neck flexor and the stabilizers on the back of the neck is thought to be upset when muscle function is compromised, which leads to a loss of the correct head and neck postural alignment. Loss of deep neck flexor endurance might lead to a bad forward head position.^[9]

Cervical extensor activity significantly increases with the forward head posture, whereas thoracic extensor activation decreases. Because the cervical extensors have a lower cross-sectional area than the extensors with a thoracic origin, their higher activation may cause the low threshold motor units of these muscles to produce less force and have less oxygenation. Some people with posture-related neck pain may exhibit increased levels of muscular activity during low-load tasks, which may be explained by the activation of higher threshold motor units, which may assist offset this fatigue response in the short term. However, increased muscle tension and stress of cervical spine components would result from the increased muscle activity, raising the risk of developing pain.^[14,15,16,45] Participants with persistent neck discomfort exhibited fatty infiltration and atrophy of the suboccipital muscles, according to research by Hallgren et al. and McPartland et al.^[27]

Teenagers frequently exhibit the forward-head, forward-shoulders posture, which continues

until old life. According to Porterfield and DeRosa, a primary cause is the weakness and lengthening of the abdominal muscles, which allows the chest to descend and shifts the weight of the upper trunk anteriorly. This is in contrast to the commonly attributed weakness or lengthening of the scapular retractors. The scapula moves forward around the rib cage as a result, forcing the clavicle on the first rib, causing the chest to drop. The head and neck are moved forward in this position, and the humerus internally rotates. The patient must extend the occiput to maintain the eyes horizontal when the head and neck are moved forward, which causes the suboccipital muscles to become overactive.^[23] Ten to fifty percent of individuals have a history of low back pain at the time of the initial evaluation of neck pain.^[3,17] There is limited evidence linking obesity to functional impairment of the spine due to lumbar muscle weakness and stiffness, which may result in LBP and disability.^[52]

The primary issues brought on by forward head posture are cervicogenic headaches and neck pain. Due to their extensive use of laptops and mobile devices, college students frequently complain of cervicogenic headaches or neck pain. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the reason for the increasing frequency of these issues. Forward Head Posture is caused by a variety of circumstances. The correlation between Craniovertebral Angle and Abdominal Endurance has been the subject of relatively little research. This study will therefore ascertain whether or whether there is a relationship between Craniovertebral Angle and Abdominal Endurance, Suboccipital Length, and Deep Cervical Flexor Strength and Endurance, all of which may increase the risk of cervicogenic headache and neck pain.

OBJECTIVES

Since more people are using laptops, smartphones, and televisions every day, forward head posture is a relatively frequent postural issue these days. A person who has a forward head posture will eventually

develop a number of linked musculoskeletal diseases. Therefore, it is important to examine and rectify forward head posture as soon as feasible. Although there are numerous factors that contribute to forward head position and associated illnesses, no study has shown one that is more likely to do so than another. The purpose of this research is to determine whether the craniovertebral angle is correlated with the strength and endurance of the short deep cervical flexors, the length of the suboccipital muscles, and the endurance of the abdominal muscles. This kind of association will be useful in illustrating which element is more likely to result in forward head posture. Therefore, we can prevent a lot of issues caused by forward head posture by changing that aspect.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Karthikeyan G et al. (2013)** chosen 25 patients with postural neck pain and 25 normal individuals aged 20 to 50 years from Mangalore. They measured Neck Disability Index, Isometric neck flexor endurance, neck extensor endurance, scapular muscle endurance and pain through visual analogue scale for subjects in both groups. They concluded that there is a significant decrease in isometric endurance of neck muscles and muscles for scapular positioning in neck pain patients.^[29]
2. **Wontae Gong et al. (2012)** conducted this study to examine the correlations between cervical lordosis angles (Absolute Rotation Angle, ARA, forward head posture, FHP, Anterior Weight Bearing, (AWB), the range of flexion and extension (RFEM), the strength and endurance of the deep neck flexor (DNF) and cervical pain. 20 male and 20 female subjects aged in 20s were selected. ARA, AWB and RFEM were analysed using radiographs of lateral views. Strength and endurance were assessed using a Pressure Biofeedback Unit (PBU) and cervical pain and physical functions were assessed using the Neck Disability Index. They concluded that the posture of the cervical spine affects the endurance

- rather than the strength of the DNF.^[49]
3. **Deepali Nivrutti Hande et al. (2012)** randomly selected 100 boys aged 11 to 14 years from 2 schools. Craniohorizontal angle (CHA), Craniovertebral angle (CVA), and Sagittal shoulder posture (SSP) with backpack and without backpack were assessed by sagittal plane photographs with help of AutoCAD software 2004. They concluded that cervical and shoulder posture were significantly alter while carrying backpack when compare the same without backpack.^[11]
 4. **Hassan Daneashmandi et al. (2012)** conducted a study on 200 randomly selected professional wrestlers 100 freestyle and 100 Greco-Roman wrestlers concluded that brief free style wrestlers suffer from more injuries compared to the Greco-Roman wrestlers, and in wrestlers with forward head were more susceptible to neck pain. It seems that the difference in craniovertebral angle in GrecoRoman and freestyle wrestles is the result of different guarding style and technique in these groups.^[24]
 5. **Stephen J. Edmondston et al. (2011)** found that Cervical and Upper Thoracic Extensor muscle activity were seen in slouched and Lumbo Pelvic Neutral Position in 23 subjects. They concluded that cervical extensor activity was higher in slouched posture whereas thoracic extensor activity was higher in lumbo pelvic neutral position than the habitual posture.^[44]
 6. **Fatma A. El-Hamalawy (2011)** included fifteen females, diagnosed as myogenic TMJ dysfunction since at least six months with limited mouth opening aged between 20-40 years (27.1 ± 4.6 years). She measured vertical mouth opening measured in millimeters by Standard ruler, pain intensity using visual analogue scale and craniocervical posture on lateral cephalometric. Each patient received exercise program consisting of 1- strengthening exercise of deep cervical flexors and scapular retractors 2- stretching exercise of the suboccipital muscles and pectoralis muscles. They concluded that independent forward head correction exercise program was effective in improving myogenic TMJD.^[18]
 7. **Anabela G. Silva et al. (2009)** conducted study over 40 non-traumatic neck pain subjects and 40 painfree subjects. Angular measurement of Craniovertebral Angle was done through the digitization of the video images. Results were concluded that younger patients with chronic nontraumatic NP were shown to have a more forward head posture in standing than matched pain-free participants.^[2]
 8. **Gwendolen A. Jull et al. (2008)** assessed the features of Activation and Isometric Endurance of Deep Cervical Flexors as well as their interactions with superficial neck flexors. They found construct validity of this method with the help of EMG. They found this test as a more selective test than the other. They concluded that the CCFT was useful in understanding the nature of impairments associated with cervical musculoskeletal disorders and developing appropriate exercise interventions for neck pain patients.^[22]
 9. **Kevin C. Parfrey et al. (2008)** collected EMG data during isometric contractions from the upper rectus abdominis, lower rectus abdominis, external abdominis, lower abdominal stabilizer, biceps femoris and rectus femoris in 14 subjects. Sit-up positions were varied and randomized. They concluded that the technique used for the Canadian Society of Exercise Physiology Health and Fitness program partial curl- or sit-up test produced the highest or equal activation levels for all abdominal muscle sites.^[31]
 10. **Martha L. Walker et al. (1987)** conducted a study on 31 healthy physical therapy students, 23 women and 8 men between the ages of 21-33 years gave the method for measuring the lumbar lordosis with a flexible curve, pelvic inclination was measured using an inclinometer concluded that there is no correlation between abdominal muscle performance, pelvic tilt and lumbar lordosis.^[33]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Study Design: Cross-sectional Study

Inclusion Criteria: Subjects having age of 18-28 years. Subjects should be asymptomatic without any musculoskeletal or neurological problem.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Any history of trauma to cervical spine since last 6 months.
- Any history of spinal deformity.
- Any history of spinal surgery.

Table1: Intrarater Reliability of Different Tests

Test	ICC Value
Photography Method [37]	0.78
Activation Score of CCFT [28]	0.81
Performance Index of CCFT [28]	0.93
Suboccipital Muscle Length Test [34]	0.939
Abdominal Endurance Test [35]	0.51

Procedure:

Using the lottery approach, 30 subjects were chosen at random for the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. They were asked to sign voluntary participation and informed consent papers. Every subject received a comprehensive explanation of the measurements that were taken. In a single session, the readings were taken in five major steps. The photography method was used to calculate head posture. The CCFT was used to measure deep cervical strength. An inclinometer was used to measure the suboccipital length. The Abdominal Endurance Test was used to test abdominal endurance.

Head Posture Measurement:

Photography Method:^[37]

The subjects were instructed to sit on the chair with their feet flat on the floor and their knees flexed to a 90-degree angle, as if they were in a typical sitting position. Ear Tragus was recognized and labeled. The subject is instructed to bend and extend their neck in order to detect the spinous process of C7. When the neck is stretched, the C7 spinous process is more noticeable while the C6 spinous process is not palpable. To make clay visible in photos, it was placed on a C7 spinous process. The tripod-mounted Kodak (M320) digital camera was two meters away from the chair. The subject's shoulder height was where the camera was positioned. For leveling, the spirit level was kept constant in the center. Then, with the neck in a neutral position, a lateral image was taken. Image Tool software was used to measure the

craniovertebral angle. Craniovertebral angle MEAN±SD is 47.66±9.75.

Cranio-cervical Flexion Test:^[28]

The individual was placed in a supine posture with their neck in a neutral position for the CCFT. In order to fill the gap between the neck and the testing surface without forcing the neck into cervical lordosis, a pressure sensor is positioned behind the neck and inflated to a standard pressure of 20 mmHg. The participant is then asked to nod (as if saying "yes") to test strength, and an increase in pressure level—known as the Activation Score—is recorded. The participant is asked to perform as many repetitions as possible at his level of endurance while holding the position for 10 seconds. The Performance Index is calculated by multiplying the level attained by the number of repeats.

Suboccipital Muscle Length Test:^[34]

The subject was instructed to place their heels, head, shoulders, and back against the wall. To preserve the curve and guarantee that action will take place above this level, both hands are positioned behind the neck curvature. The subject's ear tragus was positioned against the inclinometer's midpoint. The inclinometer's reading was recorded. To isolate the movement at the top cervical vertebrae, the individual was then instructed to nod. The Inclinometer was used to take the reading once more. The Upper Cervical Flexion range was the difference between these two readings. It is considered normal to have 10–20 degrees of range of motion.

Abdominal Endurance Test: ^[35]

The participant was instructed to high sit—that is, sit on the edge of the couch with their legs dangling down—without using any back support. He was told to get into a semi-recoiling stance by bringing his legs up to his chest (hip flexion with knee flexion). Using a

measuring tape, the individual was instructed to lift their legs by approximately 4 inches from the couch's edge. The subject was instructed to assume this position at the examiner's "start" signal, and the stopwatch recorded the time until the subject dropped or said "stop."

RESULTS

Correlation Tables:

Table2: Correlation between CVA & Different Variables

Variable	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	P
CVA & DCF Strength	0.303	0.103
CVA & DCF Endurance	0.197	0.296
CVA & SOL Length	-0.020	0.915
CVA & Abdominal Endurance	0.259	0.167

Result shows that there is no correlation between CVA with DCF Strength & Endurance, SOL Length and Abdominal Endurance.

Abbreviations:

CVA= Craniovertebral Angle

DCF= Deep Cervical Flexors

SOL= Suboccipital Length

CONCLUSION

The study's findings indicate that there is no discernible relationship between craniovertebral angle and the strength and endurance of the short deep cervical flexors, suboccipital muscle length, or abdominal endurance.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no disclosed conflicts of interest for the writers.

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REFERENCES

1. A Beer, Treleaven J, Jull G; 2012; Can functional postural exercise improve performance in the cranio-cervical flexion test? – A preliminary study; *Manual Therapy*; 17; 219-224. DOI: [10.1016/j.math.2011.12.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.math.2011.12.005)
2. Anabela G. Silva, T. David Punt, Paul Sharples, Joao P. Vilas-Boas, Mark I. Johnson; April 2009; Head Posture and Neck Pain of Chronic Nontraumatic Origin: A Comparison Between Patients and Pain-Free Persons; *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*; 90; 669-674. DOI: [10.1016/j.apmr.2008.10.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2008.10.018)
3. Barqlund Anita, Lars Alfredsson, Irene Jensen, J David Cassidy, Ake Nygren;

- August 2001; the association between exposure to a rear-end collision and future health complaints; *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*; 54(8); 851-856. DOI: [10.1016/s0895-4356\(00\)00369-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0895-4356(00)00369-3)
4. BL Braun, Amundson LR; April 1989; Quantitative assessment of head and shoulder posture; *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*; 70(4); 322-329.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2930348/>
 5. CA Oatis; *Kinesiology: The Mechanics and Pathomechanics of Human Movement*; Philadelphia, Pa: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2004.
<https://ot.lwwhealthlibrary.com/book.aspx?bookid=1738>
 6. Caneiro Joao Paulo, Peter O'Sullivan, Angus Burnett, Avi Barach, David O'Neil, Orjan Tveit, Karolina Olafsdottir, 2010, The influence of different sitting postures on head/neck posture and muscle Activity, *Manual Therapy*, 15, 54-60. DOI: [10.1016/j.math.2009.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.math.2009.06.002)
 7. Clark Boyd, Briggs, Galea; April 2002; Muscle Spindle Distribution, Morphology, and Density in Longus Colli and Multifidus Muscles of the Cervical Spine; *Spine*; 27(7); 694-701. DOI: [10.1097/00007632-200204010-00005](https://doi.org/10.1097/00007632-200204010-00005)
 8. Cote Pierre, J. David Cassidy, Linda Carroll; 2003; The epidemiology of neck pain: what we have learned from our population-based studies; *Journal of Canadian Chiropractic Association*; 47(4).
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2504974/>
 9. D Falla, Jull G, Russell T; April 2007; Effect of neck exercise on sitting posture in patients with chronic neck pain; *Physical Therapy*; 87; 408-417. DOI: [10.2522/ptj.20060009](https://doi.org/10.2522/ptj.20060009)
 10. Damaging effects of Forward Head Posture; FHP_ Revised.
https://www.physio-pedia.com/Forward_Head_Posture
 11. Deepali Nivrutti Hande, Neesha Shinde, S.M. Khatri, Pallavi Dangat; June 2012; The Effect of Backpack on Cervical and Shoulder Posture in Male Students of Loni; *International Journal of Health Sciences & Research*; 2(3).
https://www.ijhsr.org/IJHSR_Vol.2_Issue.3_June2012/9
 12. DH Watson, Trott PH; 1993; cervical headache: an investigation of natural head posture and upper cervical flexor muscle performance; *Cephalalgia*; 13; 272-84. DOI: [10.1046/j.1468-2982.1993.1304272.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1468-2982.1993.1304272.x)
 13. Dover Geoffrey, Michael E. Powers; December 2003; Reliability of Joint Position Sense and Force-Reproduction Measures during Internal and External Rotation of the Shoulder; *Journal of Athletic Training*; 38(4):304-310.
[14737211](https://doi.org/10.14737211)
 14. Edmondston Stephen J. , Michael Sharp , Andrew Symes , Nawaf Alhabib & Garry T. Allison; February 2011; Changes in mechanical load and extensor muscle activity in the cervico-thoracic spine induced by sitting posture modification; *Ergonomics*, 54:2, 179-186. DOI: [10.1080/00140139.2010.544765](https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2010.544765)
 15. EF Hodson Tole, Wakeling JM; January 2009; Motor unit recruitment for dynamic tasks: current understanding and future directions; *Journal of comparative physiology; B, Biochemical, systemic and Environmental physiology*; 179(1); 57-66. DOI: [10.1007/s00360-008-0289-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00360-008-0289-1)
 16. Elliott James, Gwendolen Jull, Jon Timothy Noteboom, Graham Galloway; 2007; MRI study of the cross-sectional area for the cervical extensor musculature in patients with persistent whiplash associated disorders (WAD); *Manual Therapy*. DOI: [10.1016/j.math.2007.01.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.math.2007.01.012)
 17. Evans R. W.; February 1998; Whiplash Injuries; *Schweizer Archieve for neurology and Psychiatry*; 149(2). DOI: [10.1007/s10194-006-0270-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10194-006-0270-x)
 18. Fatma A. El-Hamalawy; 2011; Forward Head Correction Exercises for Management of Myogenic Temporomandibular Joint Dysfunction; *Journal of American Science*; 7(8); 71-77.
https://www.jofamericanscience.org/journals/amsci/am0708/008_6307am0708_71_77.pdf
 19. Gordon Susan J, Patricia Trott , Karen A Grimmer; 2002; Waking cervical pain and stiffness, headache, scapular or arm pain: Gender and age effects; *Australian Journal*

- of Physiotherapy; 48; 9-15. DOI: [10.1016/s0004-9514\(14\)60277-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0004-9514(14)60277-4)
20. Griegel-Morris Patricia, Keith Larson, Krissann Mueller-Klaus, Carol A Oatis; June 1992; Incidence of Common Postural Abnormalities in the Cervical, Shoulder, and Thoracic Regions and Their Association with Pain in Two Age Groups of Healthy Subjects; *Physical Therapy*; 72(6); 425-431. DOI: [10.1093/ptj/72.6.425](https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/72.6.425)
21. Grimmer Karen, Pat Trott; 1998; The association between cervical excursion angles and cervical short flexor muscle endurance; *Australian Journal of Physiotherapy*; 44(3); 201-207. DOI: [10.1016/s0004-9514\(14\)60380-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0004-9514(14)60380-9)
22. Gwendolen A. Jull, Shaun P. O'Leary, Deborah L. Falla; September 2008; Clinical assessment of the deep cervical flexor muscles: the craniocervical flexion test; *Journal of Manipulative and Physiological Therapeutics*; 31(7). DOI: [10.1016/j.jmpt.2008.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmpt.2008.08.003)
23. Hammer Warren; August 1999; Forward Head/ Forward Shoulders; *Dynamic Chiropractic*; 17(18). <https://dynamicchiropractic.com/article/36230-forward-head-forward-shoulders>
24. Hassan Daneashmandi, Hossein Pirani, Siyamak Amiryan, Abolfazl Kargar; 2012; The Examination of Lower Extremity Injuries in Freestyle and Greco-Roman Wrestlers and the Relationship between Neck and Low Back Pain with Craniovertebral and Lumbosacral Angle; *Iranian Journal of Health & Physical Activity*; 3(1); 56-61. <https://www.noormags.ir/view/fa/articlepage/1015714/>
25. Hertling Darlene, Randolph M. Kessler; Management of Common Musculoskeletal Disorders: Physical Therapy Principles and Methods; 3rd edition. https://books.google.co.in/books/about/Management_of_Common_Musculoskeletal_Dis.html?id=sB3ybDCS5rgC
26. JL Silverman, Rodriquez AA, Agre JC; August 1991; Quantitative cervical flexor strength in healthy subjects and in subjects with mechanical neck pain; *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation*; 72(9); 679-681. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1859264/>
27. JM Mcpartland, Brodeur RR, Hallgren RC; January 1997; Chronic neck pain, Standing balance and Suboccipital muscle atrophy- A Pilot Study; *Journal of Manipulative and Physiological Therapeutics*; 20(1); 24-29. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9004119/>
28. Jull Gwendolen A., PT, PhD, Shaun P. O'Leary, PT, PhD, and Deborah L. Falla, PT, PhD; September 2008; Clinical assessment of the deep cervical flexor muscles: the craniocervical flexion test; *Journal of Manipulative and Physiological Therapeutics*; 31(7). DOI: [10.1016/j.jmpt.2008.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmpt.2008.08.003)
29. Karthikeyan G, Nazhath P, Selvamani K; April 2013; Isometric endurance of neck muscles and muscles for scapular positioning in individuals with and without postural neck pain; *The Internet Journal of Allied Health Sciences and Practice*; 11(2); 1-11. DOI: [10.46743/1540-580X/2013.1441](https://doi.org/10.46743/1540-580X/2013.1441)
30. Kettler A, E Hartwig, M Schultheib, L Claes; March 2002; Mechanically simulated muscle forces strongly stabilize intact and injured upper cervical spine specimens; *Journal of Biomechanics*; 35(3); 339-346. DOI: [10.1016/s0021-9290\(01\)00206-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9290(01)00206-8)
31. Kevin C. Parfrey, David Docherty, R. Chad Workman, David G. Behm; July 2008; The effect of different sit- and curl-up positions on activation of abdominal and hip flexor musculature; *Journal of Applied Physiological and Nutritional Metabolism*; 33; 888-895. DOI: [10.1139/H08-061](https://doi.org/10.1139/H08-061)
32. Maffit Christopher J, Ted Lane; April 2001; an examination of the role of the Rectus Capitis Posterior Minor Muscle in the etiology and management of Cervicogenic Headaches: A Review of Literature. DOI: [10.1016/j.spinee.2013.06.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spinee.2013.06.011)
33. Martha L. Walker, Jules M. Rothstein, Sheryl D. Finuken, Robert L. Lamb; April 1987; Relationship between lumbar lordosis, pelvic tilt & abdominal muscle performance; *Journal of American Physical Therapy Association*; 67(4); 512-516. DOI: [10.1093/ptj/67.4.512](https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/67.4.512)

34. ML Palmer, Epler ME. Fundamentals of Musculoskeletal Assessment Techniques. 2nd Ed. Baltimore: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 199. <https://pt.lwwhealthlibrary.com/book.aspx?bookid=1177>
35. Moreland Julie, Elspeth Finch, Paul Stratford, Brad Balsor, Caroline Gill; October 1997; Interrater Reliability of Six Tests of Trunk Muscle Function and Endurance; Journal of Orthopaedic and Sports Physical Therapy; 26(4). DOI: [10.2519/jospt.1997.26.4.200](https://doi.org/10.2519/jospt.1997.26.4.200)
36. MS Conley, Meyer RA, Bloomberg JJ, Feedback DL, Dudley GA; December 1995; Noninvasive analysis of human neck muscle function; Spine; 20(23); 2505-2512. DOI: [10.1097/00007632-199512000-00009](https://doi.org/10.1097/00007632-199512000-00009)
37. Niekerk Sjan-Mari van, Quinette Louw, Christopher Vaughan, Karen Grimmer-Somers and Kristiaan Schreve; August 2008; Photographic measurement of upper-body sitting posture of highschool students: A reliability and validity study; BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders; 9; 113. DOI: [10.1186/1471-2474-9-113](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2474-9-113)
38. Panjabi Manohar M., Jacek Cholewicki, Kimio Nibu, Jonathen Grauer, Lawrence B Babat, Jiri Dvorak; January 1998; Critical Load of the Human Cervical Spine: an in vitro experimental study; Clinical Biomechanics; 13(1); 11-17. DOI: [10.1016/s0268-0033\(98\)00033-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0268-0033(98)00033-3)
39. PM Barton, Hayes KC; July 1996; Neck flexor muscle strength, efficiency, and relaxation times in normal subjects and subjects with unilateral neck pain and headache; Archives of Physical and Medicine Rehabilitation; 77; 680-687. DOI: [10.1016/s0003-9993\(96\)90008-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0003-9993(96)90008-8)
40. RA Bonney, Corlett EN; September 2002; Head posture and loading of the cervical spine; Applied Ergonomics; 33(5); 415-417. DOI: [10.1016/s0003-6870\(02\)00036-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0003-6870(02)00036-4)
41. Rabin Alon, James J. Irrgang, G. Kelley Fitzgerald, Adam Eubanks; September 2006; The Intertester Reliability of the Scapular Assistance Test; Journal of Orthopaedic and Sports Physical Therapy; 36(9); 653-660. DOI: [10.2519/jospt.2006.2234](https://doi.org/10.2519/jospt.2006.2234)
42. Silva Anabela G., T. David Punt, Paul Sharples, Joao P. Vilas-Boas, Mark I. Johnson; April 2009; Head Posture and Neck Pain of Chronic Nontraumatic Origin: A Comparison Between Patients and Pain-Free Persons; Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation; 90; 669-674. DOI: [10.1016/j.apmr.2008.10.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2008.10.018)
43. Silva Anabela G., T. David Punt, Paul Sharples, Joao P. Vilas-Boas, Mark I. Johnson; January 2009; Head posture assessment for patients with neck pain: Is it useful? International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation; 16(1). DOI: [10.12968/ijtr.2009.16.1.37939](https://doi.org/10.12968/ijtr.2009.16.1.37939)
44. Stephen J. Edmondston, Michael Sharp, Andrew Symes, Nawaf Alhabib & Garry T. Allison; February 2011; Changes in mechanical load and extensor muscle activity in the cervico-thoracic spine induced by sitting posture modification; Ergonomics; 54(2); 179-186. DOI: [10.1080/00140139.2010.544765](https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2010.544765)
45. V Johnston, Jull G, Souvlis, Jimmieson NL; March 2008; Neck Movement and Muscle Activity characteristics in Female Office Workers With Neck Pain; Spine; 33(5); 555-563. DOI: [10.1097/BRS.0b013e3181657d0d](https://doi.org/10.1097/BRS.0b013e3181657d0d)
46. Vasavada Anita N., Siping Li, Scott L. Delp; 1998; Influence of Muscle Morphometry and Moment Arms on the Moment-Generating Capacity of Human Neck Muscles; Spine; 23(4); 412-422. DOI: [10.1097/00007632-199802150-00002](https://doi.org/10.1097/00007632-199802150-00002)
47. W Chansirinukor, Wilson D, Grimmer K and Dansie B; 2001; Effects of backpacks on students: Measurement of cervical and shoulder posture; Australian Journal of Physiotherapy; 47; 110-116. DOI: [10.1016/s0004-9514\(14\)60302-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0004-9514(14)60302-0)
48. weon Jong Hyuck, Jae Seop Oh, Heon Seock Cynn, Yong Wook Kim, Oh Yun Kwon, Chung Hwi yi, October 2010; Influence of forward head posture on scapular upward rotators during isometric shoulder flexion, Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies, 14(4), 367-374. DOI: [10.1016/j.jbmt.2009.06.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2009.06.006)

49. Wontae Gong, Changsook Kim, Yoonmi Lee; 2012; Correlations between Cervical Lordosis, Forward Head Posture, Cervical ROM and the Strength and Endurance of the Deep Neck Flexor Muscles in College Students; Journal of Physical Therapy and Science; 24(3); 275-277. DOI: [10.1589/jpts.24.275](https://doi.org/10.1589/jpts.24.275)
50. WY Lee, Okeson JP, Lindroth J; 1995; the relationship between forward head posture and temporomandibular disorders; Journal of Orofacial Pain; 9(2); 161-167. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7488986/>
51. Yip Chris Ho Ting, Thomas Tai Wing Chiu, Anthony Tung Kuen Poon; 2007; The relationship between head posture and severity and disability of patients with neck pain; Manual Therapy. DOI: [10.1016/j.math.2006.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.math.2006.11.002)
52. Zaina Fabio, Luca Vismara, Veronica Cimolin, Marcello Crivellini, Manuela Galli, Paolo Capodaglio, Stefano Negrini; Quantitative analysis of the effects of obesity and low back pain on gait in female patients; Italian Scientific Spine Institute. DOI: [10.1186/1743-0003-8-55](https://doi.org/10.1186/1743-0003-8-55)